

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FORMATION OF COMBAT STRESS IN MILITARY SERVANTS

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Abstract. The content of the concept of combat stress, the features of its formation, and its components are put forward in the article. In particular, the role of psychological and physiological factors that cause combat stress in military personnel is revealed. Also, features of influence of combat stress-increasing and accelerating factors on service activities in military personnel are shown.

Key words: stress, combat stress, emotional sphere, military service, subjective, action, vegetative, emotional stress, training-combat, social, ethnic, religious, family, severe stress.

Аннотация. В статье выдвинуто содержание понятия боевого стресса, особенности его формирования, его составляющие. В частности, раскрывается роль психологических и физиологических факторов, вызывающих боевой стресс у военнослужащих. Также показаны особенности влияния факторов, повышающих и ускоряющих боевое напряжение, на служебную деятельность военнослужащих.

Ключевые слова: стресс, боевое напряжение, эмоциональная сфера, военная служба, субъективное, действие, вегетативное, эмоциональное напряжение, учебно-боевое, социальное, этническое, религиозное, семейное, напряженное напряжение.

Combat stress is an emotional state of military personnel that occurs as a response to psychotraumatic factors affecting combat conditions.

Mental disorders associated with chronic experiences in terrifying situations are characterized by specific disorders, and the following components can be distinguished:

- subjective: different experiences;
- moving: description of pose, facial expressions, movement activity;
- vegetative: reactions of cardiovascular, respiratory and other systems;
- biochemical: specific aspects of metabolism.

Emotional stress is a component of military personnel's adaptive responses to changing external conditions. Under normal conditions, neuro-emotional stress helps military personnel to perform a number of professional tasks, and at the same time, the process of mobilizing the body's resources takes place. This state

of mental activity guarantees the successful completion of training-combat and combat missions.

In addition, emotional stimuli have physiological limits that are accompanied by disturbances in physiological and biochemical processes, mental functions and personality behavior. This has a negative impact on military professional activity, up to a neuro-emotional explosion.

Exceeding this limit leads to different types of disorders, which can be conditionally divided into 3 groups [2]:

- 1) emotional-motor disorder is characterized by the manifestation of general tightness or, on the contrary, disorder directed at the posture of tension in the coordination of movements;
- 2) emotional-sensory disorder appears in slowing down of the process of perception, inability to concentrate, inability to perceive commands;
- 3) emotional-intellectual disorder is characterized by slowing of thinking, decrease in criticality, manifestation of unmotivated actions, memory loss, forgetting even the simplest instructions.

Emotional stress is physiologically determined by the organism's inadequate response to external stimuli (for example, concern for life, uncertainty of the situation, hunger, etc.).

The reaction of military personnel to stressors in combat conditions depends, on the one hand, on the strength and duration of the effects, and on the other hand, on the individual-psychological characteristics of the military personnel, his psychological and military-professional preparation for conducting military operations, the character and level of motivation (taking into account the general attitude to this military conflict taking).

Among the factors affecting the acceleration of military stress in military activities, the following can be distinguished:

- a) the level of combat activity determined by the amount of combat actions in which a particular serviceman participated and threatened his life;
- b) specific aspects of the military operations in which the serviceman participated and the level of tension;
- c) the number of military losses in the part of the military service, in addition, depends on the perception of the degree of orientation and orientation to the conditions of military activity.

The following factors can negatively affect the degree of manifestation of military stress in certain military personnel: injuries and contusions inflicted on them, injuries, level of radiation, capture.

At the same time, psychologists distinguish a number of factors that increase the manifestation of military stress in military personnel: social, ethnic, religious, family and other circumstances. They are as follows [1]:

- a) lack of popularization of military conflicts among the population of the country whose citizens are military servicemen and participants in military operations;
- b) the number of servicemen with negative experiences who experienced military stress in the past;
- c) the nationality or ethnic similarity of the military serviceman with the enemy's personnel (especially if he belongs to the least common nationality in his country);
- d) the similarity or closeness of the military serviceman's religious beliefs with the enemy's personnel (especially if it is the least widespread sect in his country);
- e) female gender of military serviceman;
- j) complex (in any case) situation in the family of military personnel;
- i) complex financial and social situation of military personnel or their relatives.

In various military personnel, depending on the factors that cause the stress state indicated above:

- a) according to the speed of manifestation: from a state of high mental tension to a state of mental injury;
- b) according to the degree of manifestation: physiological, psychophysiological, psychological;
- c) according to the field of manifestation: motivational, emotional-volitional, behavioral;
- g) according to the military's understanding of its situation;
- d) according to the control of the manifestation of military stress in military personnel;
- e) according to the duration of manifestation;
- j) according to the impact on the effectiveness of military activity (high or low) and other types are distinguished.

Most military personnel can handle mild combat stress. At the initial stage, it even increases the combat activity of the military. Later, low-intensity combat stress becomes primary for participants in military operations or becomes high-intensity combat stress.

High intensity combat stress makes it difficult for military personnel as well as the military community. Individual levels of high-intensity combat stress are both external and internal.

External:

- acute, inadequate conditions that increase or, on the contrary, decrease military activity;
- inadequate military situation that increases emotional arousal or, on the contrary, weakens it ("numbness");
- manifestation of the motivation of military activity in a destructive form ("hatred of death") or, on the contrary, saving one's life in any situation;
- uncharacteristic rudeness of a particular military serviceman, destructive communication, arrogance, indiscipline;
- loss of orientation to the situation, time and space during the battle (forgetting the time, where one is at the moment);
- very rudeness, mischievousness, aggressiveness;
- obvious inhumanity, depression, apathy;
- strong psychological stress, etc.

Inside:

- perception of unreality of reality;
- a rapid increase in the feeling of anxiety, inability to overcome the feeling of fear;
- inability to concentrate;
- anxiety, confusion, etc.

The group level of high-intensity combat stress not only increases the number of military personnel experiencing stress, but also leads to qualitative changes in the socio-psychological situation in the military unit. This is primarily manifested in the following negative situations:

- the number of conflicts increases rapidly;
- the state of organization and mutual use among military personnel will quickly decrease;
- there is a negative attitude towards the military tasks being carried out;
- there is a nervous mood, a state of confusion.

To sum up, the concepts discussed above show that the social-psychological, economic, situational and personal factors of stress, combat stress (mental tension, nervous tension) are related in a complex relationship. At the same time, stress helps to more clearly reveal the causes of combat stress and, based on this, to develop measures to prevent this condition.

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